

Welcome to the Gathering for Open Science Hardware (GOSH) Community!

The purpose of this document is to help new members get involved in the GOSH Community, by succinctly highlighting key aspects of GOSH, including events, communication channels, publications, and other resources. If you have any questions, feel free to reach out via email to the GOSH Community Coordinator at brianna@openhardware.science.

What is GOSH and Open Science Hardware?

GOSH

GOSH is a global community of researchers, hardware developers, educators, community scientists, and more dedicated to making open science hardware ubiquitous by 2025. One of the hallmarks of the GOSH Community is its annual Global Gatherings that have been held all around the world! If you'd like to know more about the GOSH Community, check out our [about page](#).

Open Science Hardware

Science hardware encompasses the tools and machinery we use for scientific endeavors (for example, a microscope or environmental sensor). Open Science Hardware refers to science hardware that is open source – or free to use, change, study, and distribute.¹

The Global Gatherings

The first GOSH Gathering was held at the [European Organization for Nuclear Research \(CERN\)](#) in 2016, and led to the creation of the [GOSH Manifesto](#), which outlines the guiding principles and values of the GOSH Community. The next Gathering was held at [Universidad Católica](#) in Santiago, Chile in 2017, and it was there that the community came together to create a [roadmap](#) outlining actions and steps needed to make open science hardware ubiquitous by 2025. In 2018, we met at [OpenFiesta](#), Tsinghua University, in Shenzhen, with the aim of growing the community. After taking a four year break, the [most recent Gathering](#) took place in Panama City, Panamá in October of 2022!

Community Calls and Open Hours

Community Calls

GOSH community calls are virtual meetings aimed to share news about the activities and projects of GOSHers around the world. The calls usually consist of two 20-minute presentations of projects or topics, followed by discussion, and time for community announcements. Community calls are held once a month, and you can see a schedule for them [here](#).

Welcome Calls

Welcome calls consist of a 20-minute onboarding presentation to help orient new members to the GOSH Community, followed by time for discussion and questions. The calls are only open to new members of the community and are capped at five participants to make the experience more personal and engaging. See a schedule for the welcome calls [here](#).

The GOSH Forum

The GOSH Forum is the main communication channel for the GOSH Community. It's the best place to meet GOSHers from all over the world, learn about regional open science hardware communities, and find out more about upcoming GOSH events. Click [here](#) to sign up to the forum!

¹This definition was adapted from the [Open Source Hardware definition](#) developed by the Open Source Hardware Association (OSHW)

Funding Programs

In 2022, GOSH hosted two funding schemes for supporting community members, the [collaborative development program](#) and [regional events funding program](#). The GOSH Collaborative Development Program is for groups working on existing or new open science hardware projects, with the aim of building collaboration with industry experts, groups, and organisations. The Regional Events Funding program is for groups that want to host an event, workshop, conference, or get-together aimed at supporting open science hardware. In 2023, the GOSH community will be hosting more funding programs for workshops and events. To find out more about these programs, check out the GOSH forum.

Publications

Members of the GOSH Community frequently host writing workshops to develop guidance on Open Science Hardware (OSCh) aimed at stakeholders who are viewed as key in enabling ubiquitous adoption of OSCh. Previous publications include [policy briefs](#) for technology transfer offices, science policymakers, and research funder audiences. GOSH has also published a [framework for running community events](#), which shares knowledge on how to run a GOSH Gathering or regional event.

Regional Communities

In addition to the broader GOSH community, there are several regional and self-organized Open Science Hardware (OSCh) communities, such as [AfricaOSH](#), [Great Lakes GOSH](#), and [reGOSH](#) (which is based in Latin America). Read more about these communities [here!](#)

First Steps to Get Involved!

Not sure where to start? Here are a few simple ways to get more involved in the GOSH Community!

Join the [GOSH Forum](#) • Attend a [Welcome Call](#) or [Community Call](#) • Sign Up to the [GOSH Newsletter](#) • Check Out [these existing open science hardware projects](#) in the Community

Key Links and Resources

- GOSH Community Forum - <https://forum.openhardware.science/>
- GOSH Manifesto - <https://openhardware.science/gosh-manifesto/>
- GOSH Roadmap - <https://openhardware.science/global-open-science-hardware-roadmap/>
- Code of Conduct - <https://openhardware.science/gosh-2017/gosh-code-of-conduct/>
- Community Calls - <https://openhardware.science/about/community-calls/>
- Welcome Calls - <https://openhardware.science/welcome-calls/>
- GOSH Monthly Newsletter - <https://openhardware.science/gosh-monthly-newsletter/>
- GOSH Twitter account - <https://twitter.com/goshcommunity>
- GOSH Youtube channel - <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCLI-5snguHaYqYjclpF9Sxg>
- GOSH Blog - <https://openhardware.science/blog/>
- List of regional and domain-specific GOSH Communities - <https://openhardware.science/communities/>
- List of open science hardware projects in the community - <https://projects.openhardware.science/>

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The GOSH Welcome Guide was created by the GOSH Community Coordinator, Bri Johns, and was last updated in February 2023.